

Theorems based on Annamalai's Binomial Coefficient and Identity

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Abstract: This paper presents the innovative binomial theorems and proofs based on Annamalai's binomial identity. The factorial function defined for non-negative integers, denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . This theorem uses the factorial function and Annamalai's binomial identity.

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1. Introduction

The factorial of a non-negative integer r is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to r . For example, $5! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 120$ and $0! = 1$.

The result of $(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)$ is multiples of $n!$, i. e., $\prod_{i=1}^n (r + i) = a \times n!$, where $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$. For example, let $n = 6$ and $r = 4$.

Then, $(4 + 1)(4 + 2)(4 + 3)(4 + 4)(4 + 5)(4 + 6) = 151200 = 210 \times 720 = 210 \times 6!$.

In general, $(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n) = k \times n!$, where k is a positive integer.

2. Binomial Theorems

The following theorem is a binomial theorem based on Annamalai's binomial identity [1-5].

Theorem 1: $\frac{(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)}{(n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r)} = \frac{n!}{r!}$, where $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

The binomial theorem is proved using the following two methods.

Method 1:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n (r + i) = (r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n) = a(n!) \quad \text{and}$$
$$\prod_{j=1}^r (n + j) = (n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r) = a(r!),$$

where a is the common positive integer in these two products.

For example,

Let $n = 5$ and $r = 3$.

Then, $(3 + 1)(3 + 2)(3 + 3)(3 + 4)(3 + 5) = 6720 = 56 \times 120 = 56 \times 5!$

and $(5 + 1)(5 + 2)(5 + 3) = 336 = 56 \times 6 = 56 \times 3!$.

The result is $\frac{(3 + 1)(3 + 2)(3 + 3)(3 + 4)(3 + 5)}{(5 + 1)(5 + 2)(5 + 3)} = \frac{5!}{3!}$, where $a = 56$.

Now, we conclude that $\frac{(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)}{(n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r)} = \frac{n!}{r!}$.

Method 2: $V_r^n = V_n^r$ is the Annamalai's binomial identity for proving this theorem.

$$\text{Here, } V_r^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(r + i)}{n!} \quad \text{and } V_n^r = \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{(n + j)}{r!}.$$

$$V_r^n = V_n^r \Rightarrow \frac{(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)}{(n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r)} = \frac{n!}{r!}.$$

Hence, the theorem is proved.

Corollary:

- i. If $n > r$, then $\frac{(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)}{(n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r)} = \frac{n!}{r!} = (r + 1)(r + 3) \cdots (n - 1)n$.
- ii. If $r > n$, then $\frac{(n + 1)(n + 2)(n + 3) \cdots (n + r)}{(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)} = \frac{r!}{n!} = (n + 1)(n + 3) \cdots (r - 1)r$.

Theorem 2: $(n + r)! = k \times n! \times r!$

Proof: $(n + r)! = r! \times (r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n)$.

We know that $(r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n) = k \times n!$, where k is a positive integer.

$(n + r)! = r! \times (r + 1)(r + 2)(r + 3) \cdots (r + n) = r! \times k \times n!$.

Therefore, $(n + r)! = k \times n! \times r!$.

Corollary:

iii. $(a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + \cdots + a_n)! = T \times a_1! \times a_2! \times a_3! \times \cdots \times a_n!$, where T is a positive integer.

3. Conclusion

In this article, novel ideas based on the Annamalai's coefficients and identities have been introduced and two theorems and proofs were given for researchers and scientists for their research and development.

References

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